

Information System Technology Plan for Net Central Game Central Panabo

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ABSTRACT

This study offers a Management Information System (MIS) designed explicitly for Net Central Game Central (NCGC) to solve its operational issues, including inadequate IT infrastructure, poor attendance monitoring, and a lack of inventory management. The research includes constructing a centralized information system that combines customer data, inventory control, and employee attendance, as well as the present company procedures and issues that have been identified. It also lists the necessary IT hardware, software, and personnel for the system to work correctly. Using this suggested approach, NCGC is anticipated to enhance its overall service quality, accuracy, and efficiency. Recommendations for system implementation and training are included in the study's conclusion to guarantee seamless adoption and sustained advantages.

Keywords: Management Information System, Attendance Tracking, Inventory Management, IT Infrastructure, Operational Efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the company

On February 28, 2013, a computer engineer who had graduated from Ateneo de Davao University founded the successful company Net Central Game Central (NCGC). The business owner has over 12 years of experience handling the business and founded the company because of his passion for computer technology, online gaming, and eSports. As a Mindanao-wide organization, NCGC began with just twenty-five units in Tagum City have since grown to operate 25 branches throughout Tagum, Panabo, Davao, Samal, Midsayap, Cotabato, Mati, Koronadal, Kidapawan, and General Santos City. The business also wants to reach more people in the Visayas and Luzon.

The Panabo branch is at Redjewel Building, Quezon St., Brgy, daily. New Pandan serves at least 20 clients, with weekend and holiday traffic being particularly strong. NCGC provides a range of consumable products, such as foods and drinks, including junk foods, cup noodles, mineral water, and, to name a few, in addition to gaming services to improve the clientele's experience. Furthermore, NCGC has nearly 100 employees across all locations, including 12 employees in the Panabo branch alone.

1.2 Current Routines and Business Processes

1.2.1 Current Routines

The main task of the business in everyday routine is to make sure the units are working, manage product inventory, and maintain the place clean. Moreover, the company operates 24 hours – the daily routines of the business divided into three shifts: morning shift (8:00 AM - 4:00 PM), afternoon shift (4:00 PM - 12:00 AM), and graveyard shift (12:00 AM - 8:00 AM) and only the morning shift requires to turn on the entire units through the central server for the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP).

1.2.2 Business Process

The business has two types of customers that are given different pricing. The first are the regular customers, who use regular units and need to pay 20 pesos per hour. The second group is the VIP Customers, customers who use premium quality units and need to pay 30 pesos per hour. VIP customers are also required to show their identification card for validation. The business also offers food and drinks such as junk foods, cup noodles, mineral water, soft drinks, and more. Moreover, the customers are required to pay at the cashier.

Table 1. Event Tables of Net Central Game
Central Panabo

Start time	End Time	Task	Duration
8:15 AM	8:30 AM	Turning on units through the server	15 minutes
8:30 AM	4:00 PM	Morning shift Working Time	7 hours and 30 minutes
4:00 PM	4:15 PM	In/Out for Morning and Afternoon Shift	15 minutes
4:15 PM	12:00 AM	Afternoon shift Working Time	7 hours and 45 minutes
12:00 AM	12:15 AM	In/Out for Afternoon and Graveyard Shift	15 minutes
12:15 AM	8:00 AM	Graveyard Shift Working Time	7 hours and 45 minutes
8:00 AM	8:15 AM	In/Out for Graveyard and Morning Shift	15 minutes

Table 1 shows the daily routine of the Net Central Game Central Panabo

2.2 Existing Technologies

Client/Server Network Model

The company currently uses a client/server network model, in which every computer unit is linked to a central server that manages user sessions, data, and system functions.

Solar Power

Solar energy systems provide some of the establishment's power, lowering electricity bills and encouraging a more environmentally responsible and sustainable operation.

2.3 Problem Found

- **Weak Attendance Management:** Employees manually take pictures during their shift and send them over the company's group chat to track attendance. This causes ineffective attendance monitoring, increases the risk of errors, and dishonesty.
- **Lack of Inventory Management:** The manual inventory method, which has been time-consuming and inconvenient for everyone, is an emerging issue in the company. As a result, this leads to inconvenience, delays, and inventory inaccuracies.
- **Lack of IT Infrastructure:** The business doesn't invest in Information Systems. This results in inefficient operations and loss of track in sales. Also, limits the business's ability to improve its management process.

2.4 Goal and Objectives

General Objective

The researchers aim to:

Implement an integrated Management Information System (MIS) to improve attendance tracking, inventory management, and overall operational effectiveness and efficiency across all NCGC branches.

Specific Objectives

The specific objective of this study is to enhance the business process and routines of the store. The researcher aims to;

- To automate shift-by-shift staff attendance tracking.
- To keep track of and oversee inventories of consumable goods.
- To centralize reporting of branch data to make decisions more quickly and effectively.

2.5 Organizational Structure

Figure 1: Organizational Structure of Net Central Game Central Panabo

1.7 Stakeholders

Figure 2: Stakeholders of Net Central Game Central Panabo

2. PROPOSED INFORMATION SYSTEMS

The researchers proposed an MIS or Management Information System for the business to boost their operations, a reliable inventory process, and real-time reporting.

2.1 Name of Information System

The proposed system is named Net Central Game Central Management Information System (NCGC-MIS). Data reporting, inventory control, and employee attendance tracking are just a few of the essential business processes that this system is intended to automate and improve. The goal of NCGC-MIS is to increase operational efficiency, decrease manual errors, and offer real-time insights for better decision-making across all business branches by integrating technologies like barcode scanning and biometric attendance.

2.2 Review of the Related Study

2.2.1 Related Literature

Recent research from Indonesia shows how important Management Information Systems (MIS) are to business decision-making and operational effectiveness. Because it has a significant impact on business processes, particularly when handling large amounts of data, MIS is a crucial tool for organizations and businesses [1]. A management information system (MIS) enables businesses to gather, store, and evaluate data to enhance their decision-making procedures [2]. For companies like Net Central Game Central (NCGC), which has several locations and provides services like food and game sales, an MIS may centralize and simplify tasks like customer support, staff attendance, and inventory control.

In Santiago City, Philippines, MIS significantly impacts inventory management effectiveness, particularly in terms of stock level accuracy and operational efficiency. Studies show that effective inventory management practices, supported by MIS, positively influence operational efficiency and financial performance of businesses [3]. Real-time stock level updates across all branches would be made possible by an MIS for NCGC, where items like food and game units require constant monitoring. This lessens the possibility of stockouts or overstocking, which may result in lost revenues or needless expenses.

In Panabo City, the lack of efficient systems for storing critical data like sales, inventory, and personnel records has left many local businesses unable to manage their operations. Net Central Game Central (NCGC) is one company that understands these difficulties, particularly when handling numerous branches and high consumer volumes. The manual methods that many still use frequently result in inefficiencies, mistakes, and delays. Despite increased knowledge of digital tools, there is still a lack of widespread use of complete Management Information Systems (MIS).

The usage of MIS and its impact on Panabo City businesses' performance have not been the subject of any in-depth studies. The absence of local data is one of the reasons why business owners are hesitant to invest in these kinds of systems. Although the need for technical innovation in corporate operations is growing, the advantages of MIS are still not fully utilized in this sector.

Research examining MIS's use in Panabo City, especially in situations like NCGC, is both vital and timely given its critical role in enhancing internal processes, productivity, and competitive

advantage. As more companies look for sustainable solutions that will help them grow and enable better resource management, it is especially important.

This study can provide a reference for local business owners and decision-makers who want to use technology to improve their operations by looking at how the installation affects organizational performance in Panabo-based companies like NCGC. Developing tangible results locally will promote MIS adoption and innovation in the city's expanding business community.

2.2.2 Related System

Existing systems that meet comparable demands should be considered while creating a Management Information System (MIS) for Net Central Game Central (NCGC). The features and functions offered by these connected systems can act as references or sources of inspiration for the suggested solution. Examples of how different MIS components can work together to improve business operations include point-of-sale, inventory management, employee attendance, and customer relationship management.

One well-liked system that is widely used by businesses that sell goods and services is the Point of Sale (POS) system [4]. A point-of-sale system is used to manage transactions, track sales, and automatically update inventory. For example, systems like Square and Lightspeed help managers make quick decisions by offering data reporting and real-time sales tracking. Integrating a point-of-sale (POS) system with the management information system (MIS) can expedite NCGC's food, beverage, and gaming services sales. This makes it possible to record important client data.

Another essential technology is the Employee Attendance and Scheduling technology. These technologies automate time tracking and produce accurate records for payroll processing [5]. Examples of solutions designed to manage multiple shifts, monitor work hours, and reduce human error in attendance reporting are Kronos and TimeDoctor. Given NCGC's 24/7 operations and shifting shift patterns, putting such a system in place will significantly improve staff management and reduce the manual effort for branch managers.

Additionally, the efficiency of organizations depends on inventory management systems [6]. With tools like Zoho Inventory and TradeGecko, users can monitor stock levels, track incoming and outgoing items, and generate restocking notifications. These features can help NCGC

manage its inventory of consumables like drinks and snacks as well as equipment like keyboards and headphones. The integration of this system with the MIS will ensure that all branches have accurate and up-to-date inventory data.

Additionally, CRM (Customer Relationship Management) systems are useful for monitoring customer preferences and interactions [7]. CRM systems, such as Salesforce and HubSpot, retain client information, arrange correspondence, and assist in customizing services according to each client's requirements. A CRM system at NCGC may handle usage history, distinguish between regular and VIP clients, and facilitate loyalty programs. This enables the company to offer a more engaging and customized client experience.

Finally, companies can benefit greatly from cloud-based MIS systems [8]. Scalability and centralized data management are provided by programs like Oracle NetSuite and SAP Business One. Managers can access company data from any location at any time with these systems, which support numerous branches. Cloud-based solutions guarantee centralized control and consistent operations for a developing company like NCGC that intends to grow across geographies. They are perfect for companies that need remote monitoring and real-time updates.

In summary, these interconnected systems show how many technologies can complement one another to support a management information system's essential feature. NCGC can establish a customized MIS that satisfies its operational requirements and fosters future expansion by examining and modifying aspects of these systems.

2.2.3 System Functionality

Management Information System offers:

- Attendance monitoring - The system tracks logins and logouts by three shifts and generates comprehensive data from branches and employees, allowing for effective, thorough, and organized attendance monitoring.
- Inventory Tracking - The technology ensures smooth inventory control by offering real-time inventory tracking and alerts for low stock levels.
- Branch Reporting Dashboard - Provide summaries for product sales and customer

volume on a daily, weekly, and monthly basis.

2.2.4 System Architecture

Figure 3. System Architecture of Net Central Game Central Panabo

2.2.5 Cost Structure

Table 2. Cost Structure

Cost Description	Cost
Operational Cost	₱40,000
Maintenance Cost	₱15,000
Total Cost:	₱ 55,000

Table 2 shows the cost structure of the economic feasibility of Net Central Game Central Panabo

3. PROPOSED IT INFRASTRUCTURE AND PEOPLEWARE

3.1 Proposed Computer Hardware Desktop Computer

A desktop computer is a personal computer that is intended for regular use at a single spot on or close to a desk due to its size and power requirements. In addition to peripherals like a monitor, keyboard, and mouse, desktop computers also have peripherals like a CPU, HDD, PSU, RAM, and other components that support their operation on the motherboard.

Table 3. Computer Hardware

Computer Hardware	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Desktop Computer	CPU - Intel Core i7-12700	₱16,350	1	₱16,350
	Motherboard -ASUS ROG Strix B660-A Gaming WiFi D4	₱12,850	1	₱12,850
	RAM - Kingston 16GB DDR4 3200MHz Fury Beast	₱2,295	2	₱4,530
	SSD - Kingston NV2 PCIE 4.0 NVME M.2 500GB SSD (SNV2S/500 G)	₱1,795	1	₱1,795
	PSU - Gigabyte P550B 550W 80+ Bronze	₱2,495	1	₱2,495
	Case - Cooler Master MasterBox MB520 Mesh	₱4,450	1	₱4,450
	Monitor - Samsung 24" Essential Monitor S3 S30GD Full-HD	₱5,295	1	₱5,295
	Keyboard + Mouse - Redragon Gaming Essentials S113	₱1,895	1	₱1,895
Biometrics	Zkteco Iface 702	₱10,454	1	₱10,454
Barcode Scanner	Zebra LS2208 Barcode Scanner	₱4,200	1	₱4,200
Overall Cost: ₱64,314				

Table 3 provides information about what computer hardware the researcher proposed to enhance the business process, and the accurate overall cost of all the computer hardware being proposed.

Biometrics

To validate employee information and track shift time, the biometrics automatically saves the fingerprint to the relevant biometric software on the main server.

Barcode Scanner

Barcode scanners are optical devices that can detect printed barcodes for consumables from their inventory, decode the data when a consumer purchases it, and transmit the information to the server, instantly updating the product's availability and remaining amount.

3.2 Proposed Operating System Platforms Windows 11 Pro

With improved features including improved device management, remote desktop access, and increased security, Windows 11 Pro is a dependable operating system made for business use. It is appropriate for Net Central Game Central's operations since it supports a variety of applications, such as those used for inventory, attendance monitoring, and customer administration. Employees don't require a lot of training to utilize Windows because many users are already familiar with it.

Table 4. Operating System

OS Platform	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Windows 11 Pro	Windows 11 Pro OEM Digital License Key Lifetime Global	₱1,595	5	₱7,975
Overall Cost: ₱ 7,975				

Table 4 provides information about what operating system the researcher proposed to enhance the business process, and the accurate overall cost of the operating system being proposed.

3.3 Proposed Enterprise Software Applications Biometric Software

The platform for managing the shifting and attendance system is the biometric software. By identifying the information recorded in the database, the fingerprint of the manager and employee is found.

Inventory Software

Systems with barcode scanners provide effective inventory management and thorough, seamless product tracking. To improve decision-making and streamline corporate processes, they also offer comprehensive sales reports.

Microsoft Software

Business flexibility and actionable insights are provided by real-time data analysis systems. The system can interact with other systems and produce

customized reports based on requirements as events happen, improving overall business intelligence and decision-making skills.

Table 5. Enterprise Software Applications

Enterprise Software	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Overseas ZKBio Access IVS Version 3.2.1	64 bits 630 Megahertz ROR Face 7.0 ZEM600 CRT-IFace702	Free	1	Free
inFlow Inventory	5 members 12,000 orders per year Barcode Scanner Integration Multiple Inventory Locations	₱19,339	1	₱19,339
Microsoft Power BI Premium Per User	Cloud and Desktop Support Real-Time Data Processing Microsoft Ecosystem Integration	₱1,330	1	₱1,330
Overall Cost: ₱20,669				

Table 5 provides information about what enterprise software application the researcher proposed to enhance the business process and, the accurate overall cost of all the enterprise software applications being proposed.

3.4 Proposed Data Management Microsoft SQL Server

It is a powerful relational database management system made to effectively handle structured data. It makes managing business-critical data, guaranteeing data integrity, facilitating sophisticated queries, and producing real-time reports possible. Its functionality in a commercial context is further improved by its integration with other Microsoft applications.

Google Drive 200GB Cloud

It offers a convenient and safe cloud storage option. For a multi-branch company like NCGC, it is possible to back up and share files, reports, and logs anytime and from any location. Additionally, it guarantees that critical files are protected against hardware malfunctions and are

readily accessible by authorized people via any internet-connected device.

and share experiences. Facebook pages are made by businesses to increase their visibility, interact with clients, and run targeted ads to increase sales.

Table 6. Data Management

Proposed Data Management	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Microsoft SQL Server	Manage databases, analyze data, and generate reports	Free	1	Free
Google Drive	200GB Cloud Storage	₱1,790 per year	1	₱1,790 per year
Overall Cost: ₱1,790				

Table 6 provides information about what data management the researcher proposed to enhance the business process, and the accurate overall cost of all the data management being proposed.

3.5 Proposed Network & Telecommunications PLDT Enterprise Broadband

It is ideal for business use with 100 devices because it offers a dedicated 1 Gbps fiber connection, ensuring fast, stable, and uninterrupted internet performance. It also includes a static IP and business-grade support for reliable operations.

Table 7. Network & Telecommunications

Proposed Network & Telecommunications	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
PLDT Enterprise Broadband	1 Gbps, Static IP, Direct Line	₱22,500/month	1	₱22,500/month
Overall Cost: ₱22,500				

Table 7 provides information about what network and telecommunications the researcher proposed to enhance the business process, and the accurate overall cost of all the network and telecommunication being proposed.

3.6 Proposed Internet Platforms Facebook

It allows users to participate in a variety of activities and is readily available on a variety of digital devices with an internet connection. Facebook is being used by businesses to promote goods and services, even though many individuals use it regularly to connect with friends and family

Table 8. Internet Platform

Proposed Internet Platforms	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Facebook	Internet-connected device, widely used for connecting people and promoting businesses through pages and targeted ads	Free	1	Free
Instagram	visual-centric platform to share photos and videos to engage audiences.	Free	1	Free
TikTok	short-form video platform to create content, ideal for business promotion and user interaction	Free	1	Free
Overall Cost: ₱0				

Table 8 provides information about which internet platforms the researcher proposed to enhance the business process, and the accurate overall cost of all the internet platforms being proposed.

Instagram

It is mainly used for posting images and videos. It can be accessed on smartphones and other internet-connected digital devices. Instagram has grown to be a popular platform for both personal and professional use, with millions of users interacting with content every day. Companies use Instagram to display their goods, services, and corporate identity through eye-catching reels, stories, and posts.

TikTok

Short-form video material is the specialty of TikTok, a social media network that is expanding quickly. It lets users make, share, and interact with artistic videos and is available on mobile devices. Due to its enormous popularity, particularly among audiences, TikTok is a perfect platform for companies looking to reach this market.

3.7 Proposed IT Manpower IT Administrator

To keep the network and servers operating efficiently and to avoid downtime, the IT administrator is crucial to the general upkeep of the IT infrastructure.

System Developer

To scale, update, and modify the MIS to meet the expanding needs of the company, the System Developer is essential.

Table 9. IT Manpower

Proposed IT Manpower	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
IT Administrator	Manages IT infrastructure, network security, and server maintenance	₱28,994 [9]	1	₱28,994[9]
System Developer	Maintains MIS, manages databases, and performs system updates	₱46,505 [10]	1	₱46,505[10]
Overall Cost: ₱75,499				

Table 9 provides information about what IT manpower the researcher proposed to enhance the business process, and the accurate overall cost of all the IT manpower being proposed.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Conclusions

The main operational issues that Net Central Game Central (NCGC) is now facing are addressed by the proposed development of a Management Information System (MIS), specifically in inventory management, attendance tracking, and IT infrastructure. With several locations around Mindanao and aspirations to expand nationally, NCGC is a developing company that needs an effective and centralized system to run its day-to-day operations. The MIS will improve decision-making, increase data accuracy, and streamline operations by integrating business applications, IT personnel, and appropriate hardware. The company's long-term growth and competitiveness in the gaming and internet café industries will be supported by this development, improving customer happiness and internal management.

4.2 Recommendations

To solve the challenges and complexities that every business encounters daily, the proposal of an information system and IT infrastructure seeks to increase productivity, decrease manual tasks, and enhance the overall effectiveness of the business.

The following recommendations are given based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. The suggested Management Information System (MIS) should be implemented immediately to address the issues of inventory control, attendance monitoring, and the absence of systematized processes.
2. Workshops, training sessions, or orientations should be planned after installation to make sure that staff members are knowledgeable and able to use the system correctly and effectively.

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EDUCATION

- 2024 - Present
DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE
 - Bachelor of Science in Information System
- 2022 - 2024
SOUTHERN DAVAO NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
 - General Academic Strand (GAS)

SKILLS

- Public Speaking
- Public Relations
- Teamwork
- Time Management
- Leadership
- Critical Thinking

LANGUAGES

- English (Intermediate)
- Tagalog (Intermediate)

PROFILE

A reliable, flexible person with excellent time management, collaboration, and critical thinking abilities. knowledgeable about preserving well-organized processes, encouraging teamwork, and guaranteeing high-quality operations. competent in public relations and public speaking, dedicated to excellence and ongoing development.

WORK EXPERIENCE

- City Agriculture Office - Panabo** 2024 - 2025
SPES Worker
 - Inspected agricultural products on a regular basis to make sure they were of a high grade. Items were checked to make sure they fulfilled the necessary requirements, and any inconsistencies were quickly fixed.
 - Maintaining a clean and hygienic workplace by adhering to cleaning guidelines, keeping equipment and supplies organized, and encouraging a productive and safe work environment.
- Post Office Panabo** 2023 - 2024
SPES Worker
 - Keeping supplies and equipment organized, following cleaning protocols, and promoting a safe and productive work environment in order to maintain a clean and hygienic workplace. Sorting products ensuring.
 - Systematically arranged packages according to priority and destination, increasing operational effectiveness and reducing delivery delays.

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EDUCATION

2024-2025 Present

DAVAO DEL NORTE SATATE COLLEGES

- Bachelor of Information System

2022-2023

NORTH DAVAO COLLEGES

- Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics

SKILLS

- Teamwork
- Leadership
- Effective Communication

PROFILE

I excel at identifying and troubleshooting computer-related issues, ensuring systems function efficiently. With a proactive approach to learning and a commitment to improving my skills, I enjoy exploring innovative solutions to technical challenges. My dedication to understanding complex concepts and applying them practically helps me contribute meaningfully to any technical environment.

WORK EXPERIENCE

LANGUAGES

- English (Intermediate)
- Tagalog (Basics)
- Cebuano (Fluent)

DIONNY KEN AWA

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Panabo City

EDUCATION

2024 - Present
DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE
COLLEGE

- Bachelor of Information System

2022 - 2024
PANABO CITY SENIOR HIGH
SCHOOL

- Information and Communications
Technology

2017 - 2021
NORTH DAVAO COLLEGES

SKILLS

- Problem solving
- Creativity
- Time Management
- Flexibility

LANGUAGES

- English (Intermediate)
- Tagalog (Intermediate)
- Cebuano (Fluent)

PROFILE

A dedicated and hardworking student committed to doing my best in school. I strive to stay focused, manage my time effectively, and continuously improve my academic performance. Even when faced with challenges, I remain motivated to learn, grow, and achieve my goals.

WORK EXPERIENCE

- **K&J Plastic Products** 2019 - 2022
Salesman
 - Develop marketing strategies that align with the company's goals and objectives.

JAVED T. DAGANDA

STUDENT

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EDUCATION

2024-Present

DAVAO DEL NORTE
STATE COLLEGE

- Bachelor of Science in Information Systems

2018-2024

JOSE TUASON JR. MEMORIAL
NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

- General Academic Strand (GAS)

2009-2018

MADAUM ELEMENTARY
SCHOOL

SKILLS

- Critical thinking
- Adaptability
- Teamwork
- Time Management
- Empathy
- Self motivation
- Active listening

LANGUAGES

- Islam (Fluent)
- Cebuano (Fluent)
- English (Intermediate)
- Tagalog (Intermediate)

PROFILE

As a student with [Orthopedic], I've developed resilience, adaptability, and problem-solving skills to navigate academic and societal challenges. My goal is to pursue a degree in [Bachelor of Science in Information System] to contribute my unique perspective and skills. I thrive in environments that prioritize accessibility, inclusivity, and innovation, and I am committed to advocating for equitable opportunities for all.

WORK EXPERIENCE

Fruit vendor

- They skillfully manage inventory, pricing, and customer interactions to maximize profits within often-limited resources. This includes understanding seasonal fluctuations in supply and demand
- Many employ strategies like attractive displays, friendly customer service, and sometimes even bartering to increase sales.

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Bunawan, Davao City

EDUCATION

2022-2024
NORTHLINK TECHNOLOGICAL
COLLEGE INC.

- TVL

2018 - 2022
BERNARDINO B. BOSQUE
NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

SKILLS

- Obedient
- Computer Literate
- Consistent

LANGUAGES

- English (Basic)
- tagalog (Intermediate)

PROFILE

A student at Davao del Norte State College, taking the course of BSIS. A working student with 1 year of experience in a printing job an athlete. A person who is consistent, focused, and has timemanagement.

WORK EXPERIENCE

BIGFISH I.NET CAFE

Printer/Xerox/etc..

2024 - PRESENT

- Provider of printing services so that anyone that walks out in the shop will have a hard copy of their Files.
- The business also provides services like: softbounds,download movies and music